

1 **Vista, an immune receptor associated with exhaustion, is silenced during transformation.**

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6 We recently discovered and described an intrinsic relationship between the senescence and exhaustion
7 programs. The range of gene expression targets encompassed by and modulated during senescence and
8 senescence evasion during replicative senescence, oncogene-induced senescence and transformation
9 included TNF superfamily receptors including OX40 and CD137 (4-1bb) that function in exhaustion in
10 immune cells. We report here identification of an immunoglobulin-type immune receptor, Vista, whose
11 expression is silenced during transformation in human cells. KRas G12V represses Vista while wild-type
12 KRas is a strong activator of Vista, indicating Vista functions at the cell surface during senescence in a
13 mechanism likely involving immune cell recruitment but that cell-extrinsic control of transformation during
14 senescence is silenced by mutant oncogenic KRas.

15 **References**

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